

PHRASEOLOGICAL EXPRESSIONS REGARDING THE CONCEPT OF "YOUTH" IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK BOTH THEIR SEMANTIC FEATURES

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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on some expressions and their spiritual characteristics that are widely used in the culture of the English and Uzbek people. Also, the characteristics of such phraseological units are highlighted on the example of phrases involving the concept of "Youth", semantic analysis of similar phrases is carried out.

In linguistics, in most cases, phrases are considered as phraseological units. It is not without reason that the national-cultural problems of the phraseological system have become the object of research of many linguists. For this reason, phraseological expressions strongly express the meaning and vividly reflect the image in them compared to the words that have their meaning.

Phraseological expressions are unique figurative expressions of clear conclusions drawn by the people based on witnessing various events in life, evaluating various actions of people, summarizing their experiences. In this regard, the works of Charles Bally, who was inspired by the ideas of his teacher F. de Saussure and dedicated to the analysis of phraseology, gained great importance in Western linguistics.¹ Later, these ideas were developed and substantiated in the studies of scientists such as A. Cowie, J. Fores, J. Sinclair, dedicated to the semantics of phraseological units.²

Sh.Bally, based on the fact that semantics is the absolute sign of phraseology, expresses the following opinion: "The external sign is more important and valuable than the internal sign."³ Its semantic feature was considered as an absolute main character in Sh.Bally's works, and the denial of its historical-semantic foundations caused discussions. But these views influenced the wider research and study of phraseological issues and its formation as a

¹ Tursunova N. Regarding the status of the language unit of Frazema // Fergana State University Scientific reports. - Ferghana, 2020. - #6. - B. 235-238. (10.00.00; No. 20)

² Journal of Advanced Research and Stability Volume: 02 Issue: 09 | Sep - 2022. P-47

³ Yoldoshev B. "Fundamentals of Phraseological Methodology" Samarkand State University/; 1999.P-86

separate science. A long time after the phraseological research of Sh.Ballining, phraseology began to form as a separate field of linguistics, and phraseological dictionaries, scientific articles, dissertations, and monographic observations devoted to its various aspects appeared. Phraseology has now become a separate field with its own research method and object of study, like grammar, lexicology, phonetics and phonology departments of linguistics.

Phraseologisms, like words, express a single meaning, but the phraseological meaning differs from the lexical meaning. Phraseological meaning consists of additional marks. Information expressed by a phraseology about a sign, action, etc. is called a phraseological meaning. For example: *Now, if we provide the fourth company with walkie-talkies, it would be great. When I heard that you are here, I didn't see anything, so I decided to fly away.*⁴ The phraseology in the first example is a sign, and the one in the second example is an action. Therefore, even when phraseological units are synonymous with words, the phraseological meaning is not equal to each other. The size of the phraseological meaning is wider and more complex than the size of the lexical meaning. In the sense of many phraseological units, it is a meaningless component of a word. For example: a hard nut to crack – a very difficult problem. (Lightning on the head means to suffer greatly). It can be seen that the meaning of these phraseology has a complete meaning, the words in the phraseology do not have independence of meaning. Therefore, even if the components of some phraseologisms change, the phraseological meaning is preserved

For example: to stand to one's guns-to stick one's guns; one money-two money-three money. The given evidence shows that although phraseologisms represent a whole meaning like words, the nature of phraseological meaning and lexical meaning is not the same. Phraseologisms have semantically different characteristics from words, so they appeared and live in the language. These interconnected words are equivalent to a compound or a sentence. The phraseological meaning understood as a whole from such a combination or sentence leads to viewing it not as a syntactic unit, but as a semantic unit. In this regard, below we will consider the semantic analysis of phraseological expressions related to the concept of "Youth".

1. Bloom of youth⁵ The most enjoyable or successful time of one's youth, likened to the bloom of a flower being its most prominent and beautiful moment. This phrase is equivalent to the phrase "youth is the golden age" in the Uzbek language, it emphasizes that youth is the happiest period, and this phrase is mostly used in the language of older people.

2. Fountain of youth (Anything reputed or promising to restore one's youth, vitality, or health, or at least the appearance there of.) also means youth, and is often used in the sense of reproof. This can be understood from the following example.

At the age of 60, your grandmother looks fantastic! She must have discovered the fountain of youth. The way they advertise these skincare products makes you think each one is the fountain of youth or something.

3. *In one's youth*, viewed as the finest, most vital, or most exemplary part of one's life.

⁴ Sh. Rahmatullayev's monograph entitled "Some issues of Uzbek phraseology". Tashkent-1966. 264 pages.

⁵ UZBEKISTAN STATE UNIVERSITY OF WORLD LANGUAGES. A.L. YUSUPOV DICTIONARY OF ENGLISH-UZBEK IDIOMS. TASHKENT, 2014

Although the given expression is the same as the expression "fountain of youth", it differs in that there is a graduonymic relationship between them. That is, both expressions are spiritual. That is, both expressions have a spiritual similarity, but they are graded in terms of coloring in the speech process.

4. *Youth is wasted on the young* (term youth is wasted on the young refers to the immaturity that comes alongside the energy of youth meaning that despite having the energy to do many good things, young people will waste that energy on silly, trivial things.) phrase acquires a negative meaning, that is, it is explained with a frown that young people spend all their energy not on productive activities, but on negative, useless activities. This phrase was first used in modern English by Oscar Wilde, and before that it was used in popular speech for thousands of years. Below, we will analyze with the help of examples how this expression is used in the speech of language users of two different layers.

The first sentence is one being said by a grandmother.

*My grandson keeps making so many mistakes even though he has the potential, it's true when they say that **youth is wasted on the young**.*

The next example is a statement being said by a teacher.

• *You need to stop ruining your chances, **youth is wasted on the young** and you are a prime example of this⁶.*

In short, although there is a grammatical similarity between phraseological expressions and words, expressions differ significantly from words in terms of meaning integrity, integrity, and the strength of negative and positive coloring. At the same time, expressions related to the concept of "Youth" are of great importance here and they form the spiritual level of speech between the speaker and the listener. In every space and time, the people create units that are short in form but have deep expressive meaning in order to name and express new concepts, to realize different social situations, or to open different aspects of existing concepts and realities.

These are, of course, expressions that have passed through many years of experience of that nation, and are understandable for that nation, people, and people. These phraseological units usually not only simply name something, but also assess its connotative (stylistic) coloring, the speaker's attitude to existence, and therefore the phraseological meaning is a specific meaning in the language. Phraseologisms, in contrast to similar syntactic structures, do not occur by free choice of words in speech, by substitution. Studying phraseological expressions from different angles and approaching them comprehensively, revealing their features, summarizing them serves to enrich our language with new expressions.

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⁶ <https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com/youth>

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